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ABSTRACT

The rate at which crimes skyrocket generally in Nigeria indicated a need of collaborative policing to manage the situation at hand. Despite this urgent need, many problems are perceived to be responsible for failure in community policing strategy in curbing urban Kano crimes. This research aimed at looking at these possible factors and how they are related to failure of the long awaited and envisaged success in crime management. Being a quantitative research, the questionnaires were administered on 400 sampling units who were purposively selected with 50 representing each of the eight local government areas that made up the study area. Analysis was made using VB-SEM-PLS Smart2.0M3 software. The results showed that inter agency problems (synergy), logistic problems, and political intervention as the independent variables possessed direct positive effects on lack of public confidence as the mediator while lack of police professional skills did not. However, all the four independent variables possessed a direct positive effects on failure of community policing as the dependent variable. As lack of public confidence mediate, interagency problem (synergy), logistic problems and political interference maintained indirect relationships with the failure of community policing while lack of police professional skills have not. Hence, to achieve efficient community policing, interagency problems should be managed, funds, adequate working tools should be provided and more personnel recruited. Similarly, acquisition of more professional skills should be one of the top priorities. Also, the policing system should not be politicised but should be allowed to take a natural course. These if maintained would restore the public confidence in the police, utilising which, community policing will be successful. Thus, this could only be achieved through collaborative efforts of both concerned authorities, NGOs, entertainment industry and the general public.

Keywords: Community policing, inter-agency problems, logistic problems, police professional skill, public confidence in the police force, and political intervention.

INTRODUCTION

Community policing has been a desirable element since the human experiences of population explosion. The idea became relevant because intelligence gathering is very vital in security provision of any society. And, achieving this could only be possible if the public is integrated into security system to provide a secured society in which they live. The term community policing therefore has evidently been made common across the globe in the contemporary times. Fleming (2009) argued that, community policing is about partnerships, consultation and building trust in communities. This as many scholars proffered, is a new style in the global policing system. It is also seen as a collaborative effort designed to solve societal crimes and disorderliness. Hence, a philosophical approach that increases interaction between the law enforcements and the public (Bull, 2014).

Further, Mackenzie and Henry (2009) provided some essential elements in effective community policing. These consist of decentralisation of responsibility within policing organisations, community engagement and proactive problem solving. Arguably, community policing issue has gradually turned a dominant of policing system (Miller & Hess, 2008; Skogan, 2004). This policing strategy continued its prevalence in other rapidly developing societies (Wu, Jiang, & Lambert, 2011). Being a modern crime management strategy, various researches indicated its effectiveness in many countries so far integrated. However, the Nigerian experience has turned different. This is because, despite its relevance, community policing has not been yielding fruitful results (Alemika, 2009).

Nevertheless, some alleged problems of community policing in the country include among other things; interagency problems (synergy), logistic problems (largely consist of funds and working tools and inadequate personnel), lack of professional skills of the police force and political intervention. These factors affect the public confidence in the police force being a viable element in modern crime management enterprise. It is against this

background, the research looks at these problems and how they affect the observed failure of community policing in urban Kano Nigeria, which is densely populated and an important commercial center in sub-Saharan African region.

Problem Statement

Societies always device means and strategies to manage the perpetrated crimes being experienced. This becomes necessary as there is no crime free society in the history of mankind. However, every human society has its own ways through which crimes get managed. Thus, community policing has become a common effective strategy across the globe (Fleming, 2009; Mackenzie & Henry, 2009; Wu, Jiang, & Lambert, 2011; Bull, 2014).

While the need of community policing became necessary in Nigeria due to high crime rates, attempts by various communities to ensure its effectiveness turn abortive. Hence, the commercial urban Kano is always at risk as lives and properties have no certainty against potential social evils. To provide effective community policing therefore, there is need to identify the reasons behind the failed efforts so far experienced. This is the backbone of this study as it is believed that, unless if the identified problems are tackled, community policing would never record a success. The research is sought to establish scientific arguments about these speculations.

The Context of Community Policing

Police are viewed as law enforcing agents whose main function is to provide security and maintain law and order in human societies (Ahmad et'al 2013). Community policing highlights the significance of active partnership between police and communities in solving problems especially crime related (Wu et al., 2011). Citizens' patrol, and hot spot policing method mobilize community resources and promote information sharing between police and the concerned communities. As captured by Mackenzie and Henry (2009), community policing involves decentralization of police structure and delegation of more authority and responsibilities. In this context, manpower is essential (Huang & Sun, 2006). Community policing comes in various aspects. Thus, it promotes police rapid responses and flexibility in patrol, suspect pursuit, and reduced public fear of crime (Renmin Gong'an Bao, 2008).

The role of the police is primary and formal while the public role is secondary and informal. Hence, the police are required to work closely with the community to prevent and control crime (Wong, 2003). Public security committees shoulder important functions of maintaining social order and settling disputes (Bracey, 1984; Jiao, 2001). As such, community policing is what both sides of police and the general public proactive in providing societal peace and harmony.

Public Perceptions of Community Policing

Existing literature on public perception on community policing around the globe was largely multi-dimensional. While some studies investigated the awareness and knowledge of the public on community policing, other studies evaluated the public ratings of the priorities of police work. Moreover, another set of studies concentrated on citizens' willingness to participate in community policing activities (Wu et al., 2011). Combining the three facets, the results paved a way toward the importance of community policing and why it should be implemented especially in developing societies like Nigeria.

Meanwhile, the common belief about the police in the country is not less than an avenue of favouritism, corruption and all sorts of infidelity (Alemika & Chukwuma, 2003). This has been different compared to the western world, United States and China and other developed countries (Alemika, 2009). Police remuneration, acquired skills, work culture, and patriotism always shape police attitude toward public service in crime management (Melissa, 2014). Ironically, the overwhelming belief in the Nigerian context is that, unless the general populace are convinced of police integrity beyond any reasonable doubt, the idea of community policing may not be efficiently absorbed. Thus, failure will continue to dominate and characterise all effort although it is so much desirable.

The Need for public support of Community Policing in Nigeria

The traditional policing model was a closed-rational system more suited to a community that developed through the conflict approach. In contrast, community policing is more reflective of an open-natural system that calls for self-help but which relied on technical assistance from security stakeholders consisting the police and traditional ruling class (Ferrandino, 2014).

Various studies in Nigeria indicated that, police agency is full of characteristics, such as low quality force, poor or inadequate working tools and unhygienic environment (Alemika & Chukwuma, 2003), resources management deficiencies (Okunola & Ojo 2012), and insufficient funding (Ladapo, 2012). Other major problems of the force as observed in a GIS urban Kano analysis include largely personnel inadequacies (Ahmed, et al, 2013).

Based on these facts, the preliminary findings unveiled some verifiable ideas. These are summarized as interagency problems (synergy), logistic problems (funds, tools and personnel), lack of professional skills of the police and political interference. These factors are alleged to effect lack of public confidence in the Nigerian police force which eventually accounts for community policing failure. In all the reviewed studies particularly in Nigeria, less has been said about the effectiveness and or the reasons behind the encountered failure of community policing in the country. Following the common belief that it is so much desirable crime management strategy around the globe is what prompted this study. It is hoped the study outcomes will help in strengthening the community policing ideas providing a more viable future plan for a safer and more secured society.

Research Hypotheses

The whole research has four hypotheses paths. They are formulated as the follows:

IV to MV Relationship

- H¹: Interagency problems (synergy) have a direct positive effect on lack of public confidence in the police.
- H²: Logistic problems have a direct positive effect on lack of public confidence in the police.
- H³: Lack of police professional skills has a direct positive effect on lack of public confidence in the police.
- H⁴: Political interference has a direct positive effect on lack of public confidence in the police.

MV to DV Relationship

- H⁵: Lack of public confidence in the police has a direct positive effect on community policing failure.

IV to DV Relationship

- H⁶: Interagency problems (synergy) have a direct positive effect on community policing failure.
- H⁷: Logistic problems have a direct positive effect on community policing failure.
- H⁸: Lack of police professional skills has a direct positive effect on community policing failure.
- H⁹: Political interference has a direct positive effect on community policing failure.

IV to MV to DV Relationship

- H¹⁰: Interagency problems (synergy) have an indirect positive effect on community policing failure.
- H¹¹: Logistic problems have an indirect positive effect on community policing failure.
- H¹²: Lack of police professional skills has an indirect positive effect on community policing failure.
- H¹³: Political interference has an indirect positive effect on community policing failure.

METHODOLOGY

A total of 400 respondents were selected via purposive sampling (Chakraborty, 2009). Such had 50 respondents representing each of the eight local governments that made up the study area. Thus, the data were collected using questionnaires only being the common method in quantitative researches (Blaikie, 2000a; 2010b). Smart PLS 2.0M3 variance based, partial least square structural equation modelling (VB PLS SEM) was utilised for analysis of the research data (Hair, Black, Babin & Anderson, 2014). As a second generation tool, it provides accurate parameter estimates for both measurement/structural model analyses (Hair, Hult, Ringle & Sarstedt, 2014).

Data Analysis

Measurement and structural research models were analysed. The former comprised of the relationships between the latent and their manifest variables while the latter indicates relationships between the latent variables (Anderson & Gerbing, 1988). Algorithm graph in figure 1 summarized these two models relationship.

Figure 1: PLS Algorithm graph

Measurement Model Evaluation

Comprised of internal consistency reliability and constructs validity to establish items reliability and constructs' accuracy (Hair, Hult, Ringle & Sarstedt, 2014).

Reliability Analysis

In the examination of internal consistency reliability, outer loadings and their respective squared coefficients (indicator reliability) are presented to depict Composite Reliability which is a more chosen way of reliability analysis in PLS. This is because, Composite reliability emphasizes individual item reliability which must be 0.5 (0.708^2) (Hair, Hult, Ringle & Sarstedt, 2014). Meanwhile, Hulland (1999) argued that, indicator reliability could be retained if it achieved 0.4 or higher and maintains a minimum of 0.70 of its corresponding Composite reliability thumb rule. Synchronising the two arguments, table 1 indicated that, all the indicators (manifest variables) in the model have fully achieved indicator reliability. On the same vein, 0.70 and above Composite reliability have also all been achieved indicating that all items are proved reliable.

Construct Validity

Convergent validity and discriminant validity are examined to indicate construct validity. While the former is examined through the outer loadings and AVE, the latter is commonly examined through Fornell-Larcker criterion which is also vindicated herein.

Convergent Validity

Hair, Black, Babin and Anderson (2010) maintained that, 0.6 or higher is the minimum outer loading coefficient in a measurement model. Hair, Hult, Ringle and Sarstedt (2014) suggested 0.70 or higher. In addition, average variance extracted (AVE) which measures the amount of variance captured by the indicators relative to the measurement error

is considered and must be 0.50 (0.708^2) and higher. Table 1 indicated that, all the outer loadings are above 0.60 while the (AVE) have achieved 0.50 and above.

Table 1: Parameter Estimates of the Measurement Model

LV	MV	Outer Loadings	IR	CR	AVE
FCP	fcp1	0.811	0.658	0.875	0.636
	fcp2	0.761	0.579		
	fcp3	0.851	0.724		
	fcp4	0.764	0.584		
IAP	iap1	0.709	0.503	0.713	0.554
	iap2	0.778	0.605		
LOP	lop2	0.852	0.726	0.825	0.702
	lop3	0.824	0.679		
LPC	lpc3	0.781	0.610	0.807	0.677
	lpc4	0.862	0.743		
LPS	lps1	0.721	0.520	0.898	0.640
	lps2	0.743	0.552		
	lps3	0.776	0.602		
	lps4	0.886	0.785		
	lps5	0.861	0.741		
PIF	pif2	0.723	0.523	0.891	0.674
	pif3	0.777	0.604		
	pif4	0.902	0.814		
	pif5	0.870	0.757		

LV = latent variable, **MV** = Manifest variable, **IR** = Indicator reliability, **CR**= Composite Reliability, **AVE**=Average Variance Extracted, **FCP** = failure of community policing, **IAP** = inter agency problems (synergy), **LOP** = logistic problems, **LPC**=lack of public confidence, **LPS**=lack of police professional skill, **PIF**=political interference

Discriminant Validity

Using Fornell-Larcker criterion, it implies that, a construct is unique and captures phenomena not represented by other varying constructs in the model. Thus, the square root of the AVE of each construct should be higher than the construct's highest correlation with any other construct. Therefore, the AVE square roots compare with the latent variables' correlation coefficients. The figures in bold in table 2 (AVE square roots) are all greater than each of the coefficients on which they have been placed. This indicates that, a discriminant validity has been fully achieved (Hair, Hult, Ringle and Sarstedt, 2014).

Table 2: Discriminant Validity

	FCP	IAP	LOP	LPC	LPS	PIF
FCP	0.797					
IAP	0.299	0.744				
LOP	0.215	0.259	0.838			
LPC	0.330	0.245	0.232	0.823		
LPS	0.148	0.099	0.000	0.093	0.800	
PIF	0.316	0.363	0.157	0.201	0.095	0.821

Diagonals (*in bold*) represent square roots of AVE while off diagonals represent correlations.

FCP = failure of community policing, **IAP** = inter-agency problems (synergy), **LOP** = logistic problems, **LPC** = lack of public confidence, **LPS** = lack of police's professional skills, **PIF** = political interference.

Structural Model Evaluation

In this evaluation, path coefficient (β); coefficient of determination (R^2); effect size (f^2) and predictive relevance (Q^2) are examined.

Paths Coefficients for Hypotheses Testing

Urbach and Ahlemann (2010) argued that, paths coefficients should exceed 0.1 to account for strong impact within the model. The significance levels were set at $p < .10$, $p < .05$ and $p < .01$. The critical values are 1.65 (significance level = 10%), 1.96 (significance level = 5%) and 2.57 (significance level = 1%) taking the confidence levels at 90%, 95% and 99% respectively. The regression paths are four that comprised of direct and indirect effects. However, the first path is independent variables to mediating variable relationship. The second is mediating to dependent. Third consists of independent to dependent. And fourth, independent to dependent through the mediating variables. The 5000 bootstrapping depicting coefficients for the paths regression effects is presented in figure 2.

Figure 2: Bootstrap Graph

Direct Effects

From the regression results, Inter-agency problems (synergy) (iap) has a direct positive effect on lack of public confidence in the police (lpc) ($\beta = 0.152, t = 2.735, p < .01$). Logistic problems (lop) that largely consist of funds and tools, possessed a direct positive effect on lack of public confidence in the police (lpc) ($\beta = 0.175, t = 3.261, p < .01$). Lack of police professional skills (lps) does not have any direct effect on lack of public confidence in the police (lpc) ($\beta = 0.067, t = 1.447, p < .05$). Political interference (pif) has a direct positive effect on lack of public confidence in the police (lpc) ($\beta = 0.112, t = 2.049, p < .05$).

Also, lack of public confidence (lpc) as a mediator possessed a strong direct positive effects on failure community policing (fcp) ($\beta = 0.226, t = 3.796, p < .01$). Inter-agency problems (synergy) (iap) has a direct positive effect on failure of community policing (fcp) ($\beta = 0.138, t = 2.501, p < .05$). Logistic problems (lop) possessed a direct positive effect on failure of community policing (fcp) ($\beta = 0.096, t = 1.789, p < .10$). Lack of professional skills of the police (lps) has a direct positive effect on failure of community policing (fcp) ($\beta = 0.095, t = 1.744, p < .10$). Political interference (pif) has a direct positive effect on failure of community policing (fcp) ($\beta = 0.197, t = 3.835, p < .01$). Overall, H¹, H², H⁴, H⁵, H⁶, H⁷, H⁸ and H⁹ are supported while only H³ is not supported. Additionally, all supported relationships are strong except H⁷ and H⁸ that have beta values < 0.1. The statistical details of all the direct effects are presented in table 3.

Table 3: Parameter Estimates of Direct Effect Relationships

Hyp	Path	Beta	SE	p value	t value	Decision
H ¹	iap -> lpc	0.152	0.056	0.003	2.735***	Supported
H ²	lop -> lpc	0.175	0.054	0.001	3.261***	Supported
H ³	lps -> lpc	0.067	0.046	0.074	1.447(ns)	Not supported
H ⁴	pif -> lpc	0.112	0.055	0.021	2.049**	Supported
H ⁵	lpc -> fcp	0.226	0.060	0.000	3.796***	Supported
H ⁶	iap -> fcp	0.138	0.055	0.006	2.501**	Supported
H ⁷	lop -> fcp	0.096	0.053	0.037	1.789*	Supported
H ⁸	lps -> fcp	0.095	0.054	0.041	1.744*	Supported
H ⁹	pif -> fcp	0.197	0.051	0.000	3.835***	Supported

Beta = regression weight, SE = standard error, ns= not significant, *t* values are computed through bootstrapping standard procedure of 5000 sub samples and 400 cases, *p* values obtained in excel "TDIST(*t* value;*df*;tails)" significance at **p* < .10, ***p* < .05, ****p* < .01. All hypotheses are one tailed.

Indirect Effects

Utilising the direct effect regression and bootstrap path coefficients, indirect effects are obtained. The results indicate that, interagency problems (synergy) (iap) possessed an indirect effect on the failure of community policing (fcp) ($\beta = 0.034$, $t = 2.149$, $p < .05$). Logistic problems that involve funds and tools have an indirect effect on the failure of community policing (fcp) ($\beta = 0.040$, $t = 2.644$, $p < .01$). However, lack of professional skills of the police force (lps) does not have any effect on the failure of community policing (fcp) ($\beta = 0.015$, $t = 1.169$, $p < .10$). But political interference (pif) possessed an indirect effect on the failure of community policing (fcp) ($\beta = 0.025$, $t = 1.682$, $p < .10$). As can be observed, all the path β coefficients shrunk to < 0.1. According to McKinnon (2008), indirect relationships always shrunk whenever a mediator is introduced between the IV and DV. The statistical details are presented in table 4.

Table 4: Parameter Estimates of Indirect Effect Relationships

Hyp	Path	Beta	SE	p value	t value	Decision
H ¹⁰	iap -> lpc-> fcp	0.034	0.016	0.032	2.149**	Supported
H ¹¹	lop-> lpc-> fcp	0.040	0.015	0.009	2.644***	Supported
H ¹²	lps -> lpc-> fcp	0.015	0.013	0.243	1.169(ns)	Not supported
H ¹³	pif -> lpc-> fcp	0.025	0.015	0.093	1.682*	Supported

Beta = regression weight, SE = standard error, ns= not significant, *t* values are computed through bootstrapping standard procedure of 5000 sub samples and 400 cases, *p* values obtained in excel "TDIST(*t* value;*df*;tails)" significance at **p* < .10, ***p* < .05, ****p* < .01. All hypotheses are two tailed.

Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

As a measure of model's predictive accuracy, it represents the exogenous latent variables' combined effects on the endogenous latent variable. Scholarly researches consider 0.75, 0.50 and 0.25 as substantial, moderate and weak (Hair, Hult, Ringle & Sarstedt, 2014). In this structural model, only three exogenous variables; interagency problems (synergy) (iap), logistic problems (lop) and political interference (pif) explained 10.7% of the variance in lack of public confidence in the police (lpc) as the mediator in the model. On the other hand, five exogenous variables; interagency problems (synergy) (iap), logistics problems (lop), lack of professional skills of the police (lps), political interference (pif), and lack of public confidence in the police (lpc) explained 21.2% of variance in failure of community policing (fcp).

Effect Size (f^2)

This is an evaluation of substantive impact of exogenous construct on the endogenous constructs when the former is omitted from the model. The PLS model effect size is measured by means of Cohen's (f^2) formula (Cohen, 1988). It is represented as;

$$\frac{[R^2 \text{ inclusive} - R^2 \text{ exclusive}]}{[1 - R^2 \text{ inclusive}]}$$

Where;

R^2 Inclusive = Variance explained coefficient when the variable is included in the model.

R^2 Exclusive = Variance explained coefficient when the variable is excluded

1 = constant

Chin (2010), argued that, in Social Science oriented researches, 2% effect sizes are small but acceptable, 5-10% moderate, while 11% and above are substantial. The effect sizes as presented in table 5 consist of IAP (1.9%), LOP (0.9%), LPS (1.0%), PIF (4.1%) and LPC (5.2%).

Table 5: Effect Size

Construct	$R^2_{included}$	$R^2_{excluded}$	(f^2)	Size
IAP	0.212	0.197	0.019	Acceptable
LOP	0.212	0.205	0.009	Weak
LPS	0.212	0.204	0.010	Weak
PIF	0.212	0.180	0.041	Small
LPC*	0.212	0.171	0.052	Small

IAP= interagency problems (synergy), **LOP**= logistic problems, **LPS**= lack of police professional skills, **PIF** = political interference, **LPC**= lack of public confidence in the police. *= The mediator effect size.

Predictive Relevance

Stone (1974) and Geisser (1975) argued that, this accurately predicts the data points of indicators in reflective measurement models of endogenous constructs. Cross-Validated Redundancy is used. It omits every d th data point in the construct's indicators and estimates the parameters with the remaining data points. The omission distance D is chosen between 5 and 10 so that the number of observations used in the model estimation divided by D is not an integer (Hair, Hult, Ringle & Sarstedt, 2014). In this study, 7 was chosen. Following thumb rule, Q^2 values must be > 0. This information is presented in table 6.

Table 6: Predictive Relevance (Q^2)

Endogenous variables		
Number of Rounds	Lack of Public Confidence	Failure of community policing
Case 1	0.085	0.133
Case 2	0.086	0.110
Case 3	0.085	0.079
Case 4	0.070	0.103
Case 5	0.066	0.142
Case 6	0.006	0.137
Case 7	0.042	0.164

*All cases were obtained by 1- SSE/SSO using blindfolding technique.

SSE = sum of squared errors.

SSO = sum of squared observations

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

From the obtained results, it is indicative that, interagency problems (synergy) threatens community policing success. Hence, police shall be made independent and free of all classical form of unnecessary intrusion by the sister agencies unless where and when necessary. Secondly, logistics problems (that largely consist of funds, working tools and personnel) is one of the major impediments to the success of community policing. It is by evaluation therefore, insufficient funding, inadequate working tools and personnel characterise our police system. Unless such problems are combatted, the system will continue to be in vain. Thirdly, political interference also obstruct the public confidence in the police. This means that, a lot of political intrusions are being made which are not healthy for the system to survive the test of time. Political misconduct should be independent of public policing as much necessary if our security system is to remain a viable treasure optimism can be invoked. In as much these problems have not been checkmated, overcoming community policing obstacles will never cease to exist.

In addition to these two factors, lack of police professional skills becomes another responsible factor that result to the failure of community policing although it appeared not to influence the loss of public confidence in the police. By implication, the general public to some extent believed in the police professional skills efficiency yet directly affecting the community policing system performances. Here, something urgent need to be done to resuscitate the public confidence from an accidental moribund.

As a whole, it is indicative that, as other agencies tamper with the police work, people lose hope and sound confusing on who does the work of who. Invariably, failure of community policing strategy is always bound to occur. Similarly, insufficient funds, working tools, and inadequate personnel as well political interference obstruct police public confidence and eventually the failure of community policing. The contribution of the current research in the academic fora cannot be overemphasised. But it could be understood that, not only the investigated factors as stated herein might be responsible for the pessimistic situation vis-à-vis community policing. Other factors may equally be important. Nevertheless, it is hoped that more scholarly argument shall be justified as with time necessary. This is envisaged to unveil more related circumstances that will augur well with the changing environment all things be equal.

CONCLUSION

Following various arguments raised by different researches on police organisations and community policing, it could be observed that, police are law enforcing agents whose main function is tied to the public in the course of social problem solving through maintenance of law and order (Ahmad et'al 2013). Similarly, its collaboration with the public to maintain peace is made significant (Huang & Sun, 2006; Renmin Gong'an Bao, 2008; Mackenzie & Henry, 2009; Wu et al., 2011). The current research was able to pinpoint the reasons behind its failure in urban Kano, Nigeria despite various attempts in the past. It is hoped that the study outcomes will be utilised to achieve effectiveness of community policing plan.

It is recommended therefore, police should be made independent; an agency free from political manoeuvre and interference by related agencies. In addition, more personnel should be recruited to re-empower security measures, more professional skills should be acquired by the police, more funds must be injected, and sufficient working tools should be provided. Likewise, public enlightenment for the need of integrated community policing toward societal protection from all evils must be the top priority. These tasks lie in the hands of relevant authorities, NGOs, and entertainment industry.

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